

Review

Research Progress on Kinetics Analysis of Hydro-Mechanical Excavator – A review

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Abstract: To this end, a progressive model was built and used to analyze the excavator's dynamic responses. The undercarriage's transverse primary central axis of inertia is represented by a new generalized coordinate that expands the mathematical model from a maximum of 5 degrees of freedom to 6. An excavator can be described by a set of six second-order nonlinear, nonhomogeneous differential equations. The differential equations describing the motion of a BTH-600 hydraulic excavator equipped with pneumatic wheels have been numerically analyzed. One of the most useful mining tools is the huge hydrodynamic excavator with a face shovel, and there has been a strong tendency in recent years toward expanding the depth to which it can dig and the force with which it can dig. To achieve this goal, this study proposes an innovative model of a face-shovel hydraulic excavator that applies stick rockers and boom linkages to effectively boost the thrust and piston travel of stick hydraulic cylinders and analyzes the kinematic and dynamic properties of this proposed machine. The excavator's size and internal structure are laid out in extensive detail. The forward and inverse Kinematics and the workspace are analyzed using the graphical integration and the loop algebra theory, and then velocities and accelerations are explored. Using Kane's equations and the equivalence principle, a dynamic mathematical model of the excavator is constructed; this model is then tested via MATLAB simulations and compared to those generated by ADAMS. It is concluded that the new face-shovel hydraulic excavator has a greater excavation range and more excavating force.

Keywords: Hydraulic excavator, Dynamics mathematical model, Kinematics, Loop algebra theory

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Introduction

Hydraulic excavators are machines designed to excavate terrain, with cyclic operation in various terrain conditions [1]. The operational objects of hydraulic excavators are loose gravel and mines. They can rapidly meet the need of possessing significant excavation and lifting force, hence they have been widely utilized in open pit and coal mining. Yet, conventional excavators [2-4] have simple structures but poor performance. Compared to conventional face-shovel equipment, the new type of hydraulic excavator has a more powerful excavating force, more efficiency, a bigger operating workspace, and the ability to primarily dig along a horizontal line [5-8]. As the problem of energy global warming and other environmental pollution becomes ever conservative, the demands continue to increase (severe). It is required and urgent to reduce the energy consumption and CO₂ emission of construction equipment, particularly hydraulic excavators, due to their high quantity, poor energy efficiency, and poor exhaust. Hence, it is required to tackle the design and optimization difficulties of the excavator structure that Kinematics and dynamics methodically study [8-14]. In the mechanism field, the topology connection and kinematic and dynamic features are crucial. There are now a number of energy-saving techniques for hydraulic excavators, and they mostly focus on the following three aspects: (i) Improving the performance of working components;

(ii) Reforming the hydraulic system;

(iii) Facilitating the power matching between the diesel engine, the hydraulic system, and the load;

Improving the performance of working components has played a significant influence in reducing fuel costs for the first aspect [13, 15-20]. Some academic and industrial research groups continue to make sequential enhancements [21-23], despite the fact that the functional components have reached a robust state. Regarding the second element, the hydraulic system, which is inherently inefficient and has excessive energy loss at the major valves, is regarded as the most important study object. Several innovative hydraulic systems, such as the negative flow control system and the positive flow control system [24-30], have increased the energy efficiency of the hydraulic excavator.

Using graph theory, rigid body dynamics, and computer technology, Haug^[9] presented the notion of multibody system dynamics, one of the most active fields of research in general mechanics, as well as a high-level review and description of the existing mechanical system^[31-37].

Evaluation of dynamic performance is a fundamental aspect of the design of mechanical systems, and the method for dynamics analysis has a direct impact on the efficacy and precision of Modeling and Simulation [38-43]. Several researchers have utilized numerous methodologies, such as Newton–Euler, Lagrange equation, Kane's equations, etc., to construct the dynamic mathematical model. Frimpong and Hu [13, 44-50] developed a dynamic model of a geomaterial-digging hydraulic shovel excavator based on Newton-Euler. Towarek^[14] created the excavator dynamics model using the Lagrange equations to examine the impact of elastic deformation during digging activities. For multibody systems, Schiehlen proposed hierarchical computation and modular modeling techniques. Xu et al^[19] examined the interactions between the variables of three distinct state spaces in Kinematics, and then developed the kinematic model of an excavator in MATLAB/Simulink. Hall and McAree^[18] presented a reliable computational approach for tracking the end-point motion of multi loop linkages near singularities for a large hydraulic excavator. Hu and Jia [19] presented an enhanced version of Kane's multibody dynamics equations. Zhu and Quanxu conducted simulation studies on the kinematics and dynamics of mechanical systems and the flat-pushing process for mining excavators. However, simulation research on excavator dynamics has been conducted using MATLAB and ADAMS [51-54]. In this work, Kane's equations are chosen for modeling because they combine the advantages of analytical mechanics and vector mechanics while ignoring potential energy, kinetic energy, and constraint reaction. The research describes a new type of hydraulic face-shovel excavator in which the thrust and travel range of the stick hydraulic cylinders can be significantly improved. The remainder of the text is structured as follows: In the part entitled Structural description and hinge arrangement, the excavator's structure and constructional parameters are specified [55-62]. Following the forward and inverse kinematics investigations, the workspace, velocities, and accelerations are examined in the Kinematic analysis portion [63]. In the

Dynamic analysis part, the dynamic mathematical model is inferred and established, and MATLAB and ADAMS simulations are done and compared. In the final quarter, some conclusions are drawn.

2. Purpose of Research

The objective of this study is to assess the current state of research on the kinetic analysis of hydraulic excavators in order to gain knowledge that can be used to increase labor efficiency, save money, and reduce environmental impacts such as environmental damage.

3 Experiment Methods

In this study, two primary experimental methodologies were evaluated in order to draw fair conclusions based on the findings and outcomes of each methodology. The dynamic mathematical model and the new type of face-shovel hydraulic excavator use stick rockers and boom linkages to improve the thrust and piston travel of stick hydraulic cylinders, together with assessments of their kinematic and dynamic properties^[64].

3.1 Experiment Field

3.1.1 Structural Description and Hinge Arrangement

Figure 3-1a depicts the schematic diagram of the new-type excavator, which consists of 9 linkages and 12 joints. The links are labeled with the numbers 1, 2, 3, etc., and the joints are labeled with the letter R and subscripts R_1, R_2, R_3 , etc^[65]. The pivoting at R_4 of the intermediate triangular links articulated on the boom is a notable design element of the arm. Unlike ordinary excavators, the new mechanism is equipped with stick rockers numbered 5 and boom linkages numbered 6. In actual mining operations, the angle range of the bucket can be expanded^[66, 67], and the length of the bucket's hydraulic cylinder can be shortened, thereby reducing the cost of the bucket's hydraulic cylinder ^[68-73]. The virtual sample model of the new-type excavator is depicted in Figure 3-1b.

Fig.3-1 (a) Schematic diagram of the new-type excavator and (b) Virtual sample model of the new-type excavator
The new mechanism's dimension variables are given in Table 3-1. They are presented as a matrix. $R_i = [x_i \ y_i]$ represents the coordinates of the hinge R_i in the relative coordinate system, whereas l_i indicates the length of the linkage or hydraulic cylinder ^[74-78].

3.1.2 Kinematic Analysis

As shown in Figure 3-2, a global coordinate O-xy for the mechanism is constructed. The mechanism is composed of four distinct planar loops: Loop L_1 , which consists of the vectors a_1, a_2 , and s_1 , is a four-bar mechanism with a single degree of freedom^[79-81]. Loop L_2 is a seven-bar mechanism with four degrees of freedom, comprised of the vectors b_1, b_2, b_3, s_1 , and s_2 . Loop L_3 is a four-bar mechanism with one degree of freedom, composed of the vectors c_1, c_2, c_3 , and c_4 . Loop L_4 , composed of the vectors d_1, d_2, d_3 , and s_3 , is a two-degrees-of-freedom, five-bar mechanism. Table 3-2 introduces a set

of internal angles matching each loop. With a balance of the arches, it is possible to build linear connections between the inner angles of loops. In accordance with the graphical modularization and loop algebra theories [82-88], Fig. 3-3 and Fig. 3-4 depict a universal mechanical kinematics analysis flow diagram known as a kinematical network[89-91]. It is possible to solve the kinematical equations of each loop and to seek for suitable inputs so that a closed-form solution of the kinematics is possible [92-94]. After constructing the kinematical equations of all independent loops and their intersections, the results of the excavator's kinematics can be acquired by traversing the kinematic network in the direction indicated by the arrows in Figures 3-3 and 3-4.

Table 3-1-Dimensional variable of the new mechanism (mm)

Sketch-map with coordinate	Coordinate value or length
<p data-bbox="609 784 788 810">Machine frame</p>	$R_1 = [0 \ 0]$ $R_7 = [1163 \ -1004]$ $R_9 = [1113 \ -586]$
<p data-bbox="695 994 766 1021">Boom</p>	$R_2 = [5100 \ 0]$ $R_5 = [4108 \ 500]$ $R_8 = [3025 \ 220]$
<p data-bbox="715 1249 775 1281">Stick</p>	$R_3 = [3600 \ 0]$ $R_4 = [1228 \ 107]$ $R_{10} = [1637 \ -383]$
<p data-bbox="651 1514 730 1545">Bucket</p>	$R_{12} = [0 \ 870]$
<p data-bbox="638 1756 721 1785">Rocker</p>	$R_6 = [870 \ 0]$ $R_{11} = [480 \ 635]$

Linkage

$$l_6 = 1040$$

Hydraulic cylinder

$$l_7 = 2000 \sim 3500$$

$$l_8 = 2450 \sim 4400$$

$$l_9 = 1550 \sim 3350$$

Table 3-2 Angle relationships in four loops

Loop	Angle	Links	Loop	Angle	Links
	-	-		β_1	b_1 and s_1
L ₁	α_1 α_2	a_1 and a_2	L ₂	β_2	b_1 and s_2
	α_3	a_1 and s_1		β_3	b_3 and s_2
	-	a_2 and s_1		β_4	b_2 and b_3
	-	-		β_5	b_2 and s_1
	-	c_1 and c_4			
L ₃	γ_1 γ_2	c_3 and c_4	L ₄	φ_1 φ_1	and d_3 d_2
	γ_3 γ_4	c_2 and c_3		φ_1 φ_1	and s_3 d_1
	-	c_1 and c_2		-	and s_3
	-	-		-	-

Fig. 3-2 The coupling loops L₁, L₂, L₃ and L₄

Fig. 3-3 Forward kinematical network

Fig. 3-4 Inverse kinematical network

3.1.3 Forward and Inverse Kinematics

The position and direction of the bucket's tip can be determined based on the forward kinematical network depicted in Fig. 3-3, as shown by equation (1).

$$\begin{cases} X_N = X_A + a_2 \cdot \cos \varphi_1 + b_2 \cdot \cos \varphi_2 + c_4 \cdot \cos \varphi_3 + d_1 \cdot \cos \varphi_4 + l_{JN} \cdot \cos \varphi_5 \\ Y_N = Y_A + a_2 \cdot \sin \varphi_1 + b_2 \cdot \sin \varphi_2 + c_4 \cdot \sin \varphi_3 + d_1 \cdot \sin \varphi_4 + l_{JN} \cdot \cos \varphi_5 \\ \Psi = \pi - \varphi_4 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{cases} X_N = X_A + l_{AF} \cdot \cos \varphi_7 + l_{FJ} \cdot \cos \varphi_6 + l_{AF} \cdot \cos \varphi_5 \\ Y_N = Y_A + l_{AF} \cdot \sin \varphi_7 + l_{FJ} \cdot \sin \varphi_6 + l_{AF} \cdot \cos \varphi_5 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

X_N and Y_N are the trajectories of the bucket's tip (N) in equation (1), and orientation is the angle between vector NJ and the positive direction of the x-axis. According to the inverse kinematical network depicted in Fig. 3-4, the inverse Kinematics is performed as depicted in equation (2).

As input values for forward Kinematics, the time-varying curves of the lengths of the three hydraulic cylinders are illustrated in Fig. 3-5. According to the forward Kinematics in equation (1), Figures 3-6 and 3-7 depict the trajectory and orientation of the tip of the bucket. It can be observed that the path remains horizontal and moves downward. The numbers '1,'2,'3,'4,'5,'6, and '7 represent the angles between the positive direction of the x-axis and the vectors AB, BF, FG, GJ, JN, FJ, and AF, respectively.

Fig. 3-5 Input values of forward kinematics

Fig. 3-6 Trajectory of the bucket's tip

Fig. 3-7 Orientation Ψ

To validate the forward and inverse solutions, the forward solution's output values are used as the input values for the inverse solution. Figure 3-8 depicts the time-varying length curves of the three hydraulic cylinders derived from the inverse Kinematics in equation (2). There are numerical examples in Tables 3-3, 3-4, and 3-5. The simulation results demonstrate that the input values of forward Kinematics correspond to the output values of inverse Kinematics and vice versa, validating the forward and inverse kinematic models [95-100].

Fig 3-8 Time-varying length curves

Table 3-3 Input values of forward Kinematics

Hydraulic cylinder	Length (mm)				
	1	2	3	4	5
S ₁	3070	3052	3034	3016	2998
S ₂	3135	3255	3375	3495	3615
S ₃	2504	2522	2540	2558	2576

Table 3-4 Output values of forward Kinematics

Position and orientation	Result				
	1	2	3	4	5
X (mm)	6675	6970	7238	7486	7716
Y (mm)	-3107	-3163	-3202	-3228	-3244
Ψ /°	138.4	137.9	137.3	136.6	135.8

Table 3-5 Output values of inverse Kinematics

Hydraulic cylinder	Length (mm)				
	1	2	3	4	5
S ₁	3070	3052	3034	3016	2998

S_2	3135	3255	3375	3495	3615
S_3	2504	2522	2540	2558	2576

3.1.4 Dynamic Analysis

Using the driving space, joint space, and configuration space, a dynamic mathematical model is derived. Figure 3-9 demonstrates the Denavit-Hartenberge^[101-110] [101-110] coordinate system. The joint space is represented as T and is composed of the joint angles. The driving space consists of the lengths of three sets of driving hydraulic cylinders, denoted as $[s_1, s_2, \text{ and } s_3] T$. The configuration space is represented as $[XN, YN,]T$ and comprises of the position and orientation of the bucket's tip (N). To simplify the computation, the masses of hydraulic cylinders, links, and rockers are disregarded and the driving forces of hydraulic cylinders are equated to joint torques^[111-113]. The following is how dynamic analyses are conducted. Subsequently, mapping relationships are formed between driving variables and joint variables^[114]. The correlations between joint torques and joint variables are determined based on Kane's equations . The mathematical correlations between the driving forces of hydraulic cylinders and the joint torques are theoretically derived based on the equivalence principle^[115].

The driving space, joint space, and configuration space are used to derive the dynamic mathematical model. The Denavit-Hartenberge coordinate system is established and shown in Fig. 3-9. The joint space is made up of the joint angles and is represented as $[\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3]T$ ^[116]. The driving space is composed of the lengths of three sets of driving hydraulic cylinders, which are represented as $[s_1, s_2, s_3] T$. The configuration space consists of the position and orientation of the bucket's tip (N) and it is represented as $[XN, YN, \Psi]T$. In order to simplify the calculation, the masses of hydraulic cylinders, linkages and rockers are ignored, and the driving forces of hydraulic cylinders are made equivalent to the joint torques. The dynamic analyses are conducted as follows. First, the mapping relationships between driving variables and joint variables are established^[117-119]. Second, based on Kane's equations,] the relationships between joint torques and joint variables are deduced. Finally, according to the equivalence principle, the mathematical relationships between driving forces of hydraulic cylinders and the joint torques are derived theoretically^[120-122].

Fig. 3-9 Workspace of traditional mechanism

3.1.5 Relation Between Driving Space and Joint Space

In the Forward and Inverse Kinematics section, the driving space and configuration space are related. According to the structure diagram of the mechanism depicted in Figure 3-10, the following mapping relationships are formed between

the driving space and the joint space: Importantly, the direction in the anticlockwise direction is positive from the positive x-direction and is drawn to the tail of each vector.

Fig. 3-10 Schematic diagram of the new mechanism

For the joint of the boom

$$\theta_1 = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{l_{AB}^2 + l_{AC}^2 - s_1^2}{2l_{AB} \cdot l_{AC}} \right) - \sigma_1 \tag{3}$$

σ_1 denotes the angle between vector AC and X_0 .

For the joint of the stick

$$l_{DF} = \sqrt{l_{AD}^2 + l_{AF}^2 - 2l_{AD} \cdot l_{AF} \cdot \cos(\theta_1 + \sigma_2)} \tag{4}$$

$$\theta_2 = \pi - \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{l_{AF}^2 + l_{AD}^2 - l_{DF}^2}{2l_{AF} \cdot l_{AD}} \right) - \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{l_{DF}^2 + l_{EF}^2 - s_2^2}{2l_{DF} \cdot l_{EF}} \right) - \sigma_3 \tag{5}$$

Here σ_2 denotes the angle between vector AD and X_0 , and σ_3 represents the angle between vector FE and vector FJ.

For the joint of the bucket

$$l_{IG} = \sqrt{l_{IF}^2 + l_{FG}^2 - 2l_{IF} \cdot l_{FG} \cdot \cos(\pi - \theta_2 + \sigma_4)} \tag{6}$$

$$\angle MGJ = \pi - \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{l_{FG}^2 + l_{IG}^2 - l_{IF}^2}{2l_{FG} \cdot l_{IG}} \right) - \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{l_{IG}^2 + l_{HG}^2 - s_{IH}^2}{2l_{IG} \cdot l_{HG}} \right) - \sigma_5 \tag{7}$$

$$l_{MJ} = \sqrt{l_{MG}^2 + l_{GJ}^2 - 2l_{MG} \cdot l_{GJ} \cdot \cos \angle MGJ} \tag{8}$$

$$\theta_3 = \pi - \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{l_{MJ}^2 + l_{GJ}^2 - l_{MG}^2}{2l_{MJ} \cdot l_{GJ}} \right) - \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{l_{MJ}^2 + l_{KJ}^2 - s_3^2}{2l_{MJ} \cdot l_{KJ}} \right) - \sigma_6 \tag{9}$$

Here σ_4 denotes the angle between vector FI and vector FA, σ_5 represents the angle between vector GH and vector GM, and σ_6 indicates the angle between vector JK and vector JN. The results show that the joint angle θ_1 is associated with s_1 , the joint angle θ_2 is related to s_1 and s_2 , and the joint angle θ_3 has relation with s_1 , s_2 and s_3 .

3.1.6 Dynamic Model of Excavator

In the analysis of the dynamic stability of the excavator, we observe a mechanical model (Fig. 3-11) of the general configuration consisting of: (1) undercarriage (2) rotary link (3) boom (4) arm and (5) bucket^[2]. The links of kinematic pairs are connected, indirectly or directly, by hydraulic actuators: hydro motor driving rotation platform (s_2) and hydraulic cylinders driving manipulator (s_3, s_4, s_5).

Fig. 3-11 Physical model of hydraulic excavator: (a) Model; (b) Real picture (1-Undercarriage (pneumatics)); 2-Rotary link (platform); 3-Boom; 4-Arm (stick); 5-Bucket)

For the shown physical excavator model, a dynamic model (Fig. 3-12) is presented, with the following assumptions:

- (i) Dynamic model of excavator is non-conservative system with stationary and ideal connections;
- (ii) Small oscillations of the system around the position of the stable balance are observed;
- (iii) Foundation supporting the excavator has elastic- damped features;
- (iv) The links of kinematic chain of excavator are rigid bodies;
- (v) Hydraulic actuators of driving mechanisms are elastic dampening elements.

Fig. 3-12 Dynamic model of hydraulic excavator: (a) Side view; (b) Top view 3.1.7

Model space

The motion of the excavator (Fig. 3-12) is defined by generalized co-ordinates q in equation (10):

$$[q] = [z_c, \varphi, \theta, \alpha, \beta, \gamma]^T \quad (10)$$

where z_c is vertical displacement of the mass center of undercarriage; φ is the angle of rotation around longitudinal main central axis of inertia O_1x_1 of undercarriage; θ is the angle of rotation around transversal main central axis of inertia O_1y_1 of undercarriage; α is the angle of manipulator boom rotation around the axis O_3y_3 of the joint to which rotary link is attached; β is the angle of manipulator arm rotation around the axis O_4y_4 of the joint in the end of the boom and γ is the angle of manipulator bucket rotation around the axis O_5y_5 of the joint in the end of the arm. It is supposed that generalized coordinates are of small size measured from the position of the stable balance of the system[123]. The critical positions of the excavator are analyzed when the plane of the manipulator is normal to longitudinal plane of undercarriage (Fig. 3-12).

3.1.8 Coordinate Systems

The position of the excavator is specified relative to the absolute, stationary coordinate system $Oxyz$. The initial O coordinate of the absolute system is located at the mass center of the undercarriage for the entire system (undercarriage, rotary link, boom, arm, and bucket). The axis Ox is directed in the direction of the longitudinal axis, the axis Oy is directed in the direction of the transverse primary central axis of inertia, and the axis Oz is directed downward vertically

[117-125]. Excavator local coordinate systems (Fig. 3-12) are created in order to determine the location of kinematic chain links.

- (i) $O_1x_1y_1z_1$ is the moving coordinate system adopted for the mass center O_1 of undercarriage. The axis Ox_1 coincides with longitudinal axis, and the axis Oy_1 with transversal main central axis of inertia of undercarriage in balance position and the axis Oz_1 is directed vertically downward.
- (ii) $O_2x_2y_2z_2$ is the moving coordinate system connected to the center of axial bearing O_2 ;
- (iii) $O_3x_3y_3z_3$ is the coordinate system connected to center of the joint O_3 and rotated for the generalized coordinate α in regard to coordinate system $O_3x_3y_3z_3$;
- (iv) $O_4x_4y_4z_4$ is the coordinate system connected to the center of joint O_4 and rotated for the generalized coordinate β in regard to coordinate system $O_3x_3y_3z_3$;
- (v) $O_5x_5y_5z_5$ is the coordinate system connected to the center of joint O_5 and rotated for generalized coordinate γ in regard to coordinate system $O_4x_4y_4z_4$.

3.1.9 Kinetic Energy of System

The kinetic energy of the system is equal to total of kinetic energies of the system segments:

$$E_k = E_{k1} + E_{k2} + E_{k3} + E_{k4} + E_{k5} \tag{11}$$

Where E_{k1} is the kinetic energy of undercarriage; E_{k2} is the kinetic energy of platform; E_{k3} is the kinetic energy of boom; E_{k4} is the kinetic energy of arm-stick and E_{k5} is the kinetic energy of bucket.

Further,

$$2E_{k1} = m_1v_1^2 + J_1x_1^{\varphi^2} + J_1y_1^{\theta^2} \tag{12}$$

$$2E_{k2} = m_2v_p^2 + J_2x_2^{\varphi^2} + J_2y_2^{\theta^2} \tag{13}$$

$$2E_{k3} = m_3v_s^2 + J_3x_3^{\alpha^2} \tag{14}$$

$$2E_{k4} = m_4v_R^2 + J_4x_4^{\beta^2} \tag{15}$$

$$2E_{k5} = m_5v_K^2 + J_5x_5^{\gamma^2} \tag{16}$$

$$2E_k = m_1v_1^2 + J_1x_1^{\varphi^2} + J_1y_1^{\theta^2} + m_2v_p^2 + J_2x_2^{\varphi^2} + J_2y_2^{\theta^2} + m_3v_s^2 + J_3x_3^{\alpha^2} + m_4v_R^2 + J_4x_4^{\beta^2} + m_5v_K^2 + J_5x_5^{\gamma^2} \tag{17}$$

Where m_i ($i=1, 2, 3, 4, 5$) is mass of particular parts of excavator: undercarriage, platform, boom, arm and bucket; v_i ($i=1, P, S, R, K$) is absolute velocity of the mass center of particular parts of the excavator: undercarriage, platform, boom, arm and bucket; J_{jx_k} ($j, k=1, 2, 3, 4, 5$) is main central axial moment of mass inertia of particular parts of the excavator for longitudinal axis O_jx_k which passes through the mass center O_j ; J_1y_1 is main central axial moment of mass inertia of undercarriage for transversal axis O_1y_1 which passes through the mass center O_1 ; J_2y_2 is main central axial moment of mass inertia of rotary link for transversal axis O_2y_2 which passes through the mass center O_2 ; φ, θ are angular velocities of undercarriage around its longitudinal O_1x_1 and transversal O_1y_1 axis of inertia, respectively^[124, 125].

4. Conclusions

The study examines the dynamics and kinematics of a model hydraulic face-shovel excavator that employs boom linkages and stick rockers to effectively extend the thrust and travel range of the stick hydraulic cylinders. The excavator's constructional dimensions and structure are designed. The kinematical network is built in accordance with the graphical modularization and loop algebra theory, which serve as the foundation for the kinematics analysis. According to the simulation results, the forward kinematic model's inputs are equivalent to the inverse kinematic model's outputs and

vice versa. Also, the workspace of horizontal digging as well as velocities and accelerations are evaluated, demonstrating that the largest workspaces occur when the orientation is maintained between 100° and 120°. The dynamic research is built on the analysis of kinematics. The dynamic mathematical model is derived and established on the basis of the equivalence principle and Kane's equations. The accuracy of the kinematic and dynamic mathematical models is further demonstrated by a comparison of the MATLAB and ADAMS simulations, which reveals that the largest inaccuracy is no greater than 2.5%. The study can help with future studies and investigations of the innovative mechanism.

This paper reviews the hydraulic excavator's dynamic behavior. Determined the degree and nature of dynamic movements, velocities, and accelerations using the dynamic-mathematical model. The sixth generalized coordinate, which represents rotation around the undercarriage's transversal axis, is added to the mathematical model of the dynamic behavior of hydraulic excavators. The analytical-mathematical model is enhanced by modeling the dynamic behavior of hydraulic excavators using a system of nonlinear differential equations, bringing the simulation closer to the actual operation of the excavator. It is imperative to do new research in order to better understand how changes in joint rigidity, mass, size, and excitation position affect dynamic behavior. Also, experimental testing of the observed system's dynamics and comparing the test results to those obtained from numerical simulation are of particular interest.

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